

**Formative Evaluation of
SSHRC's Research/Creation in
Fine Arts Program**

Methodology Appendix

October 8, 2007

Science-Matrix
& Manon Bourgeois

**Formative Evaluation of SSHRC's
Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts Program**
Methodological Appendix

Science-Metrix & Manon Bourgeois

Formative Evaluation of SSHRC's Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts Program

Methodological Appendix

October 8, 2007

by

Éric Archambault, D.Phil.

Frédéric Bertrand, M.Sc.

Manon Bourgeois, M.Sc. and,

Julie Caruso, M.L.I.S.

submitted to the

Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC)

Science-Metrix specializes in the measurement and evaluation of research. We perform program and policy evaluations and performance measurement, benchmarking and sector analyses, market studies and strategic planning. Our data collection and assessment methods include bibliometrics, scientometrics, technometrics, surveys, interviews, environmental scans, monitoring and intelligence gathering.

514.495.6505 ▪ 1335A Mont-Royal Avenue E. ▪ Montreal ▪ Quebec ▪ Canada ▪ H2J 1Y6
info@science-metrix.com ▪ www.science-metrix.com

Photography Artist: Stefan Denis, Montreal, Quebec, Canada ▪ Title: la vallée du silence (Mixed technics: 58x60 in.) ▪ www.furaxe.qc.ca

Table of Contents

Table of Contents i
Annex A – Methodological Approach 1
Annex B – Roundtable Workshop Program 5
Annex C – Roundtable Participation Feedback 12
Annex D – Survey Questionnaire: Funded Applicants 14
Annex E – Survey Questionnaire: Unfunded Applicants 35
Annex F – Survey Questionnaire: Managers and Grant Officers 49

Annex A – Methodological Approach

Documentation and File Review

The following types of documentation, files, and data were systematically reviewed:

- **Contextual Information:** These documents provided background information on the research and funding environment prior to and at the time of the program's inception, as well as the initial conception and formation of the program. Examples of this information include: the 1994 Report of the SSHRC-Canada Council Committee on the Review of Access to Support for the Fine Arts Community; information on the *Programme de Soutien aux regroupements de recherche-cration* and the *Programme d'appui  la recherche-cration* of the FQRSC; information on the Arts and Humanities Research Boards' Research Grants Scheme; report on SSHRC's Artist-University Research Alliance; information on SSHRC's Strategic Programs and Joint Initiatives; reports by the SSHRC Sub-Committee on the Creative and Fine Arts; and a paper citing examples of creative research by academically-based artists in the fine arts.
- **Program Documentation:** These documents provided information on program delivery, such as: print-outs of the program information page from the SSHRC Web site; program updates and highlights; summaries and handouts for Canada Council information sessions; workshop and conference agendas and handouts; summaries of the proposed research of successful applicants); and application forms and instructions.
- **Grant Applications:** Selected applications were provided in full, with the exception of supplementary material, and resulting adjudication/feedback letters for most were also provided.
- **Competition Results:** Selected statistics on the competition results for all three rounds were provided. Examples included: applicant statistics; success/result statistics; amounts requested and granted (2006 round).
- **Internal SSHRC Correspondence:** This category included correspondence between SSHRC staff, such as: drafts and discussions of program descriptions; a list of critical path activities and dates; emails between SSHRC employees; minutes and follow-up notes of meetings (meetings with Council or staff orientation meetings); proposed revisions for the second round (concerning eligibility, evaluation criteria, etc.); summaries of implemented changes from round 2 to round 3; information on program updates; the report on the Summary and Recommendations from the Council for the Approval of the Pilot Program (March 2003); memorandums; and the report of an observer of the adjudication committee for the 2005 competition.
- **External Correspondence:** This category primarily comprised e-mails between SSHRC employees and representatives from other funding agencies/organizations; students, deans, research administrators, and other representatives of universities; members of the press, etc.
- **Newsletters:** Many issues of the CAFAD Newsletter (of the Canadian Association of Fine Arts Deans) were provided, as some included articles about the program, with specific examples of research or commentary.
- **Other Documentation and Data:** Documentation on other similar funding programs (internationally and in Canada, etc.) and data on Canadian artistic research setting (Graduate survey data from Statistics Canada).

Roundtable Workshop

Key information for this evaluation was obtained in a roundtable workshop. The central goal was to enable SSHRC and the evaluation practitioners to gather firsthand accounts of grantees' experiences

Methodological Appendix

throughout the grant process. An ancillary goal of the event was to heighten mutual understanding between SSHRC grant recipients and SSHRC personnel. It was also an important process for examining key evaluation issues and/or raising unforeseen research questions/hypotheses for this pilot program evaluation. The incentive for the use of this primary data collection instrument is that it facilitates brainstorming and “thinking out of the box” to examine and explore a wide range of issues and shared concerns related to this SSHRC pilot program. The event took place on March 23rd, 2007 at SSHRC/NSERC headquarters in Ottawa, with 23 people in attendance. The evaluation team was responsible for selecting and inviting roundtable participants. Present were 12 artist-researchers, selected to represent as broad a span of criteria as possible with respect to such conditions as artistic discipline and geographical location, institution size, gender and team or individual projects (see Table I). In addition, four of the artist-researchers had applied to the program twice, with an unsuccessful result in the first round and a successful result in the second.

Table I Distribution of participants by artistic discipline, province, institution size, gender, team or individual projects, and of “successful status”

Discipline	Participant	Institution size	Participant
Architecture	2	Large	7
Arts Education	2	Medium	2
Dance	1	Small	2
Literature	1	College	1
Media and Electronic Arts	1		
Theatre, Drama	1		
Visual Arts	4		
		Gender	Participant
		Female	6
		Male	6
Province	Participant	Team/Individual	Participant
Alberta	4	Individual	4
British Columbia	1	Team	6
Manitoba	1		
Nova Scotia	1		
Ontario	2		
Quebec	3		
		Successful after being rejected	Participant
		Unsuccessful 2003/Successful 2005	4

Together with the roundtable President, three of the 12 artist-researchers were members of the program’s EAC, and one was a grant holder from the Research/Creation program. Ten observers were also present, including the Acting Director of the EAC, a program manager from the FQRSC, a grant officer from Ryerson University, a member of the SSHRC council, SSHRC program manager, evaluation officers, three evaluators from the evaluation team. The roundtable discussion, which lasted approximately five hours (from 9:30 am to 4:30 pm, with two hours for lunch and breaks that facilitated informal discussions), was structured around four themes. Participants (and occasionally observers, when appropriate) discussed and debated 1) key definitions, 2) program objectives, 3) impact of funding, and 4) program management and outreach. The discussion was concurrently recorded and the substantive information was later transcribed in order to enable review and analysis. The roundtable has been invaluable in providing insight into the development of the subsequent web surveys and provided a strong complement of information to other evaluation instruments.

Web Survey of Funded and Unfunded Applicants (Comparable Group)

The surveys were posted on the Web and made available in both official languages and in two formats: HTML and text. Respondents were invited to participate in the survey with complete anonymity. All applicants to the program received an invitation letter by e-mail notifying them of the availability of the survey, which was accessible through a hypertext link. A total of 413 names and e-mail contacts were provided by SSHRC using administrative data. The survey population of funded applicants comprised 90

Methodological Appendix

grantees and the population of unfunded applicants, the comparable group, comprised 323 unsuccessful applicants, including 42 applications that were judged ineligible in the application process.

On May 15th, applicants funded by the program in competition years 2003 and 2005 were invited to participate and received an e-mail reminder two weeks later. On May 24th, funded applicants from the 2006 competition were invited and received an e-mail reminder one week later. The survey was closed on June 8th. Grantees from the 2006 competition were not asked questions related to program outcomes and impacts because they had not time to advance in their funded projects. From May 28th to June 13th, unfunded applicants from all three competition years were invited to participate and were reminded by e-mail. A total of 64 funded and 102 unfunded applicants completed the surveys.

Science-Metrix managed the list of e-mail addresses for the survey population, in addition to dealing with a number of bounced e-mails due to a series of technical and non technical issues (invalid e-mail addresses, e-mail host servers and auto-responders). Each bounced invitation was treated in order to find a valid substitute e-mail through multiple sources and to resend an invitation to complete the survey. This way, all funded applicants were contacted, but it was not possible to find valid alternate e-mails for 61 unfunded applicants and one unfunded applicant was found to be deceased. Because of this, the number of reachable unfunded applicants was 260 out of the total population of 323 unfunded applicants.

The distribution of survey respondents' is actually highly representative of the characteristics of the population of artist-researchers who have applied to the program (Table II).

Table II Distribution of respondents by region and by institution size

Region	Unfunded applicants	Funded applicants	Total applicants	Sample %	Population %	Δ (Survey-Population)
Atlantic	6	6	12	7.1%	7.8%	-0.7%
Quebec	19	14	33	19.6%	21.3%	-1.7%
Ontario	38	20	58	34.5%	36.5%	-2.0%
Prairies	16	8	24	14.3%	14.6%	-0.3%
British Columbia	25	16	41	24.4%	19.6%	4.8%
Total	104	64	168	100.0%	100.0%	

Institution size	Unfunded applicants	Funded applicants	Total applicants	Sample %	Population %	Δ (Survey-Population)
Large-size university	42	36	78	46.4%	44.9%	1.5%
Medium-size university	34	17	51	30.4%	28.3%	2.1%
Small-size university	16	5	21	12.5%	16.9%	-4.4%
University College	2	2	4	2.4%	2.3%	0.1%
Community College	2		2	1.2%	1.9%	-0.7%
Other	7	4	11	6.5%	5.5%	1.1%
No answer	1		1	0.6%	0.2%	0.4%
Total	104	64	168	100.0%	100.0%	

Web Survey of Post-Secondary Institutions: Research Managers/Grants Officers

The aim of the survey of academic institutions was to include administering organization that host clients of the program and to shed light on the efficiency of current promotion methods used to publicize the existence of the program. It was also used to obtain another point of view on the way the program is designed, delivered, and managed. The issues that have been examined in this survey also include the needs for and current support available to artist-researchers for applying to the program and suggestions for its improvement.

Methodological Appendix

Contact information of university managers/grant officers were provided by respondents of the surveys of applicants through a standalone question asked once questionnaires were submitted. Applicants were asked to provide the name and contact information for the person in charge of supporting artist-researchers in the competition process as well as providing liaison with SSHRC for the SSHRC Research/Creation in the Fine Arts Program funding opportunity.

Originally, 142 contacts have been provided by funded and unfunded applicants. After removing duplicates, contact information for 76 university managers/grant officers was validated using the Web. These were invited to complete the survey on June 16th and a reminder was sent by email about a week later. This survey ended on June 28th. From 76 invitations, 27 representatives from post-secondary institutions completed the survey: 11 from large-size universities, 9 from medium-size universities and 7 from small-size universities and one from other type of institution. In terms of regional distribution, 11 respondents were from Ontario, 7 from British Columbia, 4 from the Prairies, 3 from Quebec and 2 from the Atlantic region.

It's not possible to determine the size of the population of resources that support artist-researcher in applying to the program. Thus, the sample size was deemed adequate for descriptive statistics only. Despite this, the data collected in this survey revealed very rich information relevant to formative evaluation issues.

Annex B – Roundtable Workshop Program

Science-Metrix & Manon Bourgeois Roundtable Workshop on SSHRC's Research/Creation Grants in the Fine Arts Pilot Program

Program and Background Information

DATE

March 23rd, 2007 ■ 9:30 am to 4:00 pm

LOCATION

Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC)

350 Albert Street ■ Ottawa ■ Ontario ■ K1P 6G4

14th Floor ■ Room 1451

PRESIDENCY

Lynn Hughes, Concordia University

CONTENTS

The President's Welcome and Introduction ■ page 1

Roundtable Workshop Program ■ page 2

Thematic Issues & Related Questions ■ page 3-4

Background Definitions ■ page 5-6

The President's Welcome and Introduction

Thank you for finding time in your extremely busy schedules to participate in the roundtable evaluation session for the SSHRC pilot program in Research/Creation. I am delighted to be involved in an event that seems so significant—both in terms of the evaluation process and the advancement of the Canadian research/creation community. This is the first time that SSHRC has used this format as part of a program evaluation process and it therefore participates in the spirit of innovation that the program was meant to encourage.

The roundtable will serve as a data collection instrument. The goal is to better understand the successes and failures of the Research/Creation program by listening to artist-researchers' comments. We are hoping to create a situation that stimulates brainstorming, or "thinking out of the box", and allows us to explore a wide range of issues related to the pilot program and the research fields it is meant to serve. We anticipate that the discussion will examine key issues and articulate issues that have been implicit up until now — as well as suggest fruitful questions and paths for this program review.

The core roundtable participants are all researchers who have been funded by the program. The group has been chosen to be as diverse and representative as possible. It includes, for example, individual and team projects, researchers who were refused initially and funded in a subsequent competition, and, most crucially, a very wide range of research/creation practices carried out in different settings.

The term research/creation is gaining currency both in Canada and internationally. Until recently, university and college based artists had been treated as research "outsiders" —an exotic, and perhaps even a suspicious, breed. Until the FQRSC in Quebec began funding research/creation in 2000, we were the only university sector excluded from the spectrum of funding programs intended for university research and researchers. A few hardy artist-researchers managed to piggy back elements of their research programs on Strategic grants in other disciplines —usually by suppressing important aspects of their activity and describing their practice in language (or with emphases) developed in very different disciplines. While artist-researchers were able to apply to the Canada Council, this was often also awkward, either because the assumptions and setting at the university are different than those for independent artists (student mentoring, for instance) or because university artists were seen as intruding on the very slim percentage of the Council funds available for independent artists' projects. At the same time, university artist-researchers are increasingly involved in interdisciplinary initiatives that cross university disciplines and may also include the participation of artists and organizations beyond the university. For these and other reasons, there is a growing recognition that artist-researchers have something very vital to contribute to the contemporary university research community.

You will see that the roundtable discussion is divided into four themes. Some of these will overlap, but the division is intended to help ensure that we cover as many of the key questions as possible. I will do my best to both direct the discussion —and, in the spirit of brainstorming, to allow for some divergence where it seems likely to prove fruitful.

Once again, we are very grateful for your willingness to dedicate your time to this. The positive responses, even at such short notice, from artists-researchers and other participants reflect the remarkable level of interest this program has generated.

SSHRC, the Evaluation Advisory Committee, and the Evaluation team wish you a very lively, interesting day.

Lynn Hughes

Lynn Hughes has been producing and exhibiting her work for over twenty years and has taught at Universities across Canada. Her undergraduate education was in English Literature and in Art, and she has a graduate degree in the History and Philosophy of Science and Technology with a concentration in the area of history and philosophy of mathematics. She is currently Associate Dean, Academic and Student Affairs, at Concordia University in Montreal and holds a Concordia Research Chair in the Studio Arts Department. She was instrumental in the conception, structuring, and funding of Hexagram, the Montreal Institute for Research/Creation in Media Arts and Technologies, and also served on the committee that lobbied for and planned the new pilot program to fund Research/Creation through the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada.

Roundtable Workshop Program

- 9h30 Arrival of participants; continental breakfast
- 9h55 Welcome and opening remarks
- 10h05 Introductory presentations (30 seconds by participant)
- 10h15 Theme 1 ■ Key definitions**
- 11h15 Theme 2 ■ Program objectives**
- 12h15 Lunch buffet – and informal discussion on the experience of participants with the program
- 13h15 Theme 3 ■ Impact of funding**
- 14h15 Coffee break
- 14h30 Theme 4 ■ Program management and outreach**
- 15h45 Roundtable conclusion
- 16h00 Roundtable adjournment

Thematic Issues & Related Questions

Theme 1 ■ Key definitions (Definitions are provided in the last section)

1. Research/Creation

- Is the SSHRC definition clear and well understood? (How could it be improved?)
- Is there a difference between research/creation and traditional creation?
- Does creation in academia have particular characteristics?
- Is the notion of a clear research question important and useful, or not?
- What about “a well considered methodological approach”?
- What does excellence mean in the context of research/creation?

2. Program of research/creation

- Is the concept of “program” clear?
- Is it more difficult to perform team research in artistic disciplines?
- Do you have other comments on this definition?

3. Artists–researcher

- What do you think of this definition?
- Is it inclusive enough?

4. Artistic discipline

- Is the definition adequate and functional?
- Is the term “artistic” appropriate for all these disciplines/areas?
- Should the area of research/creation be identified as in the Fine Arts?

Theme 2 ■ Program objectives (Definitions are provided in the last section)

- What do “advancement of knowledge” and “innovation” mean in research/creation?
- Does this program enhance your ability to mentor and train students? Is this an important aspect of the program?
- What do you understand by “dissemination ... to a broad public”, and how have you approached this in your research?
- Is the objective of collaboration (with independent artists, other disciplines or institutions) easy or difficult to meet?
- Are there other programs (municipal, provincial, national or international) that you can apply to for research/creation funding? How do these compare to the SSHRC program?
- Are all these criteria relevant and should they have the same weight?

Theme 3 ■ Impact of funding

- How has this program affected the way you perform research in academia?
- Has it affected the way you train and mentor students?
- Has it had an impact on the recognition of your research -both within and beyond your home institution?
- How does/might this program affect the artistic community?
- What is the potential for research funded by this program to have an impact beyond this? (Has it, or could it eventually have an impact on other university disciplines, or broader extra-institutional cultural or socio-economic impacts?)

Theme 4 ■ Program management and outreach

- How appropriate are the value and duration of the grants?
- Do you have comments on the evaluation process –including the information you received after the competition?
- Did you encounter specific problems submitting or managing the grant, relative to the rules and forms provided or required by SSHRC?
- What do you think of the CV format you are required to submit?
- Is there a need to provide different guidelines for the use of funds in different disciplines?
- Is SSHRC promoting the program adequately and appropriately?
- Do you think it would be possible or desirable to redefine the requirements and selection process of this program so that it could be converted into a SSHRC standard research program?

Miscellaneous comments

- Are there any important aspects linked to your experience with this program, or suggestions to improve it, that we have not discussed?

Other comments or suggestions?

If you feel that you did not have the opportunity at the roundtable to share and discuss particular issues of interest to you, you are invited to share your thoughts on those issues with the evaluation team at info@science-metrix.com

Acronyms

FQRSC: Fonds québécois de la recherche sur la société et la culture (FQRSC)

UQAM: Université du Québec à Montréal

SSHRC: Social Science and Humanities Research Council

EAC: Evaluation Advisory Committee

CPE: Corporate Performance, Evaluation and Audit

SPJD: Strategic Programs and Joint Initiatives

Background Definitions (for theme 1 and 2)

Theme 1 ■ Key definitions

1. Research/creation

SSHRC Definition

"Definition of Research/creation (RC): any research activity or approach to research that forms an essential part of a creative process or artistic discipline and that directly fosters the creation of literary/artistic works. The research must address clear research questions, offer theoretical contextualization within the relevant field or fields of literary/artistic inquiry, and present a well considered methodological approach. Both the research and the resulting literary/artistic works must meet peer standards of excellence and be suitable for publication, public performance or viewing."

Definition by FQRSC

By research-creation, the *Fonds Société et Culture* refers to research activities or approaches fostering the creation or interpretation of literary or artistic works of any type. Within the context of this program, interpretation is analogous to creation and cannot be understood as an intellectual approach of analysis of a creator's work or achievements.

A research-creation approach in arts and letters depends on the exercise of sustained creative practice; on intrinsic reflection on the development of previously unpublished works or productions; and on the dissemination of these works in various forms. A research-creation approach must contribute to disciplinary development by a renewal of knowledge or know-how, and innovations of an aesthetic, pedagogical, technical, instrumental or other nature. These activities must contribute, from the peer review standpoint:

- to the development of each form of expression, on condition that the works, the approach followed, the style, the forms of expression, the technology or material used, the modes of presentation, the repertory or the style of interpretation offer evolution, originality, innovation or renewal in relation to the present state of the specific field;
- to the training of students, particularly at the postgraduate levels;
- to an increased recognition of the stakeholders in the field of arts and letters;
- to the enrichment of the Québec, Canadian or international cultural heritage.

2. Artist-researcher

"An artist-researcher is a person affiliated with a Canadian postsecondary institution, member of the faculty of a Canadian postsecondary institution whose work involves research, the creation of works of art, and the training of undergraduate and/or graduate students. Where their work is similar to that of full-time faculty, and where the institution agrees, this may include adjunct, part-time, sessional and emeritus faculty as well as university-employed curators."

3. Artistic discipline

"Artistic discipline specifics to the Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program: any one, or any combination of, the following categories: architecture, design (including interior design), creative writing, visual arts (painting, drawing, sculpture, ceramics, textiles), performing arts (dance, music, theatre), film, video, performance art, interdisciplinary arts, media and electronic arts, and new artistic practices."

4. Program of research/creation

"The program of research/creation: a sustained research enterprise that includes one or more projects or other components, and which is shaped by broad objectives for the advancement of knowledge in the fine arts, through the development or renewal of the field of artistic endeavour concerned. It might be undertaken primarily by one investigator and encompassed within a single research career, or it could mobilize a team of researchers during a specific period. In pursuit of the overall objectives, specific approaches and methods are advanced, adopted and modified as the research proceeds and as findings are made and reported. SSHRC will support new and ongoing programs of research/creation through grants of up to three years of duration, based on peer-review judgment of the probable significance of the contribution to knowledge in the relevant disciplines."

Theme 2 ■ Program objectives

"SSHRC recognizes that artist-researchers work in an academic setting and that, like their colleagues in other fields, their duties focus on two broad functions: contributing to the development or renewal of their field, and training undergraduate and graduate students. Accordingly, the program's specific objectives are to:

- **support high-quality research/creation** in projects that advance knowledge in the fine arts and enhance the overall quality of artistic production in Canadian postsecondary institutions;
- **develop the research skills of graduate and undergraduate students** who are working in artistic and related disciplines through their participation in programs of research that involve artistic practice;
- **facilitate the dissemination and presentation of high quality work** to a broad public through a diversity of scholarly and artistic means; and,
- **foster opportunities for collaboration** among university- and college-based artist-researchers, other university and college researchers, and professional artists. "

Annex C – Roundtable Participation Feedback

Roundtable participants (n=14) were asked to answer a feedback/response form at the end of the workshop. As indicated by the feedback received, the response to the roundtable was overwhelmingly positive. None of the participants marked ‘disagree’ or ‘strongly disagree’ to any of the items on the feedback form. This suggests that participants found the roundtable to be useful, relevant, positive, and suitably arranged. It also supports the idea that the coordination regarding travel, accommodation, meals, and roundtable content that took place between the consulting company Science-Metrix and SSHRC’s staff was professional and of high quality.

Given the degree of agreement and praise from roundtable participants, it is difficult to make specific critical statements about the process and results of the roundtable, barring that people felt positively about their experience. Overall, the item that participants most strongly agreed with was item 8 (*I had the impression that my time was used in a worthwhile manner*), with only 14% indicating less than strong agreement. The second highest rated item was the program and timetable (nine strongly agreeing, four agreeing). Given the complexity of the issues addressed and the speed at which the roundtable was planned and organized, it would have been virtually impossible to better tailor the program and timetable beforehand. In addition, given that there were no objections or criticisms of either, it appears that there is no need to further refine the program or timetable. Ratings of events peripheral to the content of the roundtable itself (travel, food, and the duration of the roundtable) were also highly praised.

The item that received the least endorsement dealt with the documents that were provided beforehand. Though all respondents agreed that they were useful, 50% strongly agreed, while 43% agreed (7% abstained). Lacking more specific feedback, it is difficult to say what could have been done to improve the information package distributed to participants.

Comments from participants were minimal; they included praise for the event, chair, evaluation team, and other participants, requests to hear more about other researcher’s work, and a suggestion that small-group discussions may have been helpful. Comments pertained to the format of the roundtable itself, rather than on the content of discussions, and would not be useful in informing the evaluation.

Without basic demographic information it is impossible to summarize results by group (i.e., advisory committee or participant).

Overall, given the overwhelmingly positive feedback from participants, both SSHRC and Science-Metrix (in partnership with Manon Bourgeois) can take great pride in the quick and professional organization of a successful roundtable workshop that will be of great use in informing the information-gathering stage of the pilot program evaluation.

Methodological Appendix

Table III Summary of roundtable feedback form responses

#	Question	Response	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Abstain	N
1	The documents provided to us before the roundtable were useful and provided adequate information	n %	7 50%	6 43%	0 0%	0 0%	1 7%	14
2	The objectives of the roundtable were clearly stated	n %	11 79%	2 14%	0 0%	0 0%	1 7%	14
3	The program and timetable were well adapted for this kind of event and facilitated open discussion	n %	9 64%	4 29%	0	0	1 7%	14
4	The themes and questions addressed during the roundtable were clear and relevant	n %	11 79%	2 14%	0 0%	0 0%	1 7%	14
5	The travel arrangements were made in a professional manner and I received the help that I needed	n %	10 71%	1 7%	0 0%	0 0%	3 21%	14
6	The food and snacks provided had the required level of quality	n %	11 79%	3 21%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	14
7	The duration of the roundtable was appropriate	n %	11 79%	3 21%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	14
8	I had the impression that my time was used in a worthwhile manner	n %	12 86%	2 14%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	14

Annex D – Survey Questionnaire: Funded Applicants

Survey Questionnaire Evaluation of SSHRC Research/Creation in the Fine Arts Pilot Program

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information from artist-researchers affiliated with Canadian postsecondary institutions who have applied to the SSHRC Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program for research grants.

Specifically, the main goal of the survey is to collect primary data on applicants' experiences with this program as well as information on the environment and conditions in which artist-researchers and students produce and evolve.

Ultimately, this survey will provide SSHRC management with data on the activities, outputs, and initial outcomes of this pilot program according to the following evaluation issues: i) program design and management, ii) program outputs and immediate outcomes, iii) program risks and opportunities, and iv) continued relevance and priorities.

This exercise constitutes the first external evaluation of the program. As such, your involvement is vital to the process.

The survey is being administered to all artist-researchers who have applied for funding in the first two competitions of this pilot program.

Please note that the individual answers provided in this survey will not be published. Rather, they will be compiled and aggregated in the analysis report.

The survey consists of 34 questions.

IMPORTANT: Please click on the "Submit" button at the end of the survey.

We thank you in advance for your cooperation.

Have a good survey!

GENERAL INFORMATION

Q1

In which artistic discipline(s) are you active?

- Architecture
- Design (including interior design)
- Creative writing
- Visual arts (painting, drawing, sculpture, ceramics, textiles)
- Dance
- Music
- Theatre, drama
- Film and video
- Media and electronic arts
- Performance arts
- Art education
- Interdisciplinary arts
- Other (*please specify below*)

Please specify (Other category):

Q2

What is the type/size of your post-secondary institution?

- Large-size university** (A large university has sponsored research expenditures of over \$30 million, a general operating percentage of over 20%, and greater than 30 doctoral programs)
- Medium-size university** (A medium university has sponsored research expenditures between \$10 million and \$30 million, a general operating percentage between 10% and 20%, and between 10 and 30 doctoral programs)
- Small-size university** (A small university has sponsored research expenditures of less than \$10 million, a general operating percentage of less than 10%, and less than 10 doctoral programs)
- University College
- Community College
- Cegep
- Other (please specify below)

Please specify (Other category):

Q3

In which Canadian region is your institution located?

- Atlantic (Newfoundland/Labrador, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia, New Brunswick)
- Quebec
- Ontario
- Prairies (Manitoba, Saskatchewan, Alberta)
- British Columbia
- Yukon, Nunavut and Northwest Territories

PROGRAM DEFINITION AND OBJECTIVES

Research/Creation has been defined by SSHRC as:

Research/creation (specific to the Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program): Any research activity or approach to research that forms an essential part of a creative process or artistic discipline and that directly fosters the creation of literary/artistic works. The research must address clear research questions, offer theoretical contextualization within the relevant field or fields of literary/artistic inquiry, and present a well considered methodological approach. Both the research and the resulting literary/artistic works must meet peer standards of excellence and be suitable for publication, public performance or viewing.

Q4 Do you find this definition appropriate as a basis for the program?

- Very appropriate
- Appropriate
- Somewhat appropriate
- Not appropriate

Q5 Could you suggest ways in which the definition could be improved?

Q6

Please rank the following program objectives according to their degree of relevance to your activities:

	<i>Very relevant</i>	<i>Relevant</i>	<i>Not very relevant</i>	<i>Not relevant</i>
Support high-quality research/creation in projects that advance knowledge in the fine arts and enhance the overall quality of artistic production in Canadian postsecondary institutions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop the research skills of graduate and undergraduate students who are working in artistic and related disciplines through their participation in programs of research that involve artistic practice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitate the dissemination and presentation of high quality work to a broad public through a diversity of scholarly and artistic means.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Foster opportunities for collaboration among university- and college-based artist-researchers, other university and college researchers, and professional artists.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q7

Should these objectives be modified to better support your research activities and the needs of artist-researchers?

Yes

No

If yes, please specify:

Q8

Please indicate the degree to which you were required to adapt/modify your research/creation project in your grant application to meet the criteria, requirements and objectives of the program:

	<i>Entirely</i>	<i>Significantl y</i>	<i>Moderately</i>	<i>Slightly</i>	<i>Not at all</i>
Artistic discipline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Area of research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research/creation questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creation program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Methodology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expected impact/results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dissemination and presentation of results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Team composition and role of collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Training of students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CV and other credentials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If other, please specify:

IMPACT OF SSHRC FUNDING

Q9 Please indicate the degree of impact funding has had on the following aspects of your artistic and research/creation activities:

	Very positive	Somewh at positive	No impact	Somewh at negative	Very negative	Not appl icable
Qualitative nature of your artistic activity	<input type="radio"/>					
Quantitative nature of your artistic activity	<input type="radio"/>					
Qualitative nature of your research-creation activity	<input type="radio"/>					
Quantitative nature of your research-creation activity	<input type="radio"/>					
Your inter- and cross-disciplinary practices	<input type="radio"/>					
Other impacts (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>					

Please specify (other impacts):

Q10 Please indicate the degree of impact funding has had on the following aspects of your training activities:

	Very positive	Somewh at positive	No impact	Somewh at negative	Very negative	Not appl icable
Providing graduate students with training and mentoring	<input type="radio"/>					
Providing undergraduate (or collegial level) students with training and mentoring	<input type="radio"/>					
Research skills of students who have participated in your project	<input type="radio"/>					
Creation skills of students who have participated in your project	<input type="radio"/>					
Development of academic programs/course curricula related to research/creation in the fine arts	<input type="radio"/>					
Development of academic programs/course curricula related to research/creation in other disciplines outside of the fine arts	<input type="radio"/>					
Other impacts (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>					

Please specify (other impacts):

Q11

Please indicate the degree of impact funding has had on the following aspects of your dissemination and presentation activities:

	<i>Very positive</i>	<i>Somewh at positive</i>	<i>No impact</i>	<i>Somewh at negative</i>	<i>Very negative</i>	<i>Not appl icable</i>
Dissemination and presentation of your work to the academic community in the fine arts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dissemination and presentation of your work to the academic community in disciplines outside of the fine arts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dissemination and presentation of your work to a broad public (<i>arts stakeholders and general public</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other impacts (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please specify (other impacts):

Q12

How many students have participated in your project?

Bachelor's level student(s)	<input type="text"/>
Master's level student(s)	<input type="text"/>
Doctorate level student(s)	<input type="text"/>
Collegiate level student(s)	<input type="text"/>
Other (<i>Please specify below</i>)	<input type="text"/>

Please specify other:

Q13

Please indicate how many CANADIAN COLLABORATORS have been involved in your project:

Academic artist-researchers from your specific discipline

Academic artist-researchers from other fine arts disciplines

Academic researchers from humanities disciplines

Academic researchers from social science disciplines

Academic researchers from natural science and engineering disciplines

Academic researchers from health science disciplines

Professional artists practicing outside of academic institutions

Other professionals outside of academic institutions

Other type of collaborator (*please specify below*)

Please specify other:

Q14

Please indicate how many INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATORS have been involved in your project:

Academic artist-researchers from your specific discipline

Academic artist-researchers from other fine arts disciplines

Academic researchers from humanities disciplines

Academic researchers from social science disciplines

Academic researchers from natural science and engineering disciplines

Academic researchers from health science disciplines

Professional artists practicing outside of academic institutions

Other professionals outside of academic institutions

Other type of collaborator (*please specify below*)

Please specify other:

Q15

Please indicate the degree of impact that funding has had on your collaborative activities with the following types of collaborators:

	Very positive	Somewh at positive	No impact	Somewh at negative	Very negative	Not appl icable
Academic artist-researchers from your specific discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Academic artist-researchers from other fine arts discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Academic researchers from humanities discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Academic researchers from social science discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Academic researchers from natural science and engineering discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Academic researchers from health science discipline	<input type="radio"/>					
Professional artists practicing outside of academic institution	<input type="radio"/>					
Professionals outside of academic institutions	<input type="radio"/>					
Other type of collaborator (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>					

Please specify other:

Q16

Please indicate the degree of impact that funding has had on the following communities:

	Very positive	Somewh at positive	No impact	Somewh at negative	Very negative	Not appl icable
The research service and management of your post-secondary institution	<input type="radio"/>					
Your immediate working environment (in your faculty)	<input type="radio"/>					
Your academic research community	<input type="radio"/>					
The research community at large	<input type="radio"/>					
The professional fine arts community (outside of post-secondary institutions)	<input type="radio"/>					
Other type of community (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>					

Please specify other type of community:

Q17

Has your funded project resulted in any innovations or socio-economic benefits?

Yes

No

If yes, please specify:

Q18

What was the knowledge and know-how that resulted from your research project?

Q19 Please indicate the main unexpected impact (positive or negative) the funding program has had on your activities?

Q20 What might be some of the long-term impacts of this program for Canadian art and creation research capabilities (and beyond)? Conversely, what might be some of the effects of not pursuing this pilot program?

PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

Q21 Please rank the following aspects of the application process according to their degree of adequacy:

	Very adequate	Adequate	Somewhat adequate	Not adequate	Not applicable
Clarity of instruction for the application process	<input type="radio"/>				
Transparency, fairness, and appropriateness of evaluation criteria	<input type="radio"/>				
Description of various categories of eligible applicants/participants	<input type="radio"/>				
Comprehensiveness of listed areas of art research/disciplines	<input type="radio"/>				
Availability of application form	<input type="radio"/>				
Amount of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>				
Ease of use of SSHRC's online CV form and related instruction	<input type="radio"/>				
Amount of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>				
Time given to complete the application	<input type="radio"/>				
Timing of application announcements/deadlines	<input type="radio"/>				
Adjudication and peer review process	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>				
Quantity of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>				
Overall SSHRC client support provided to applicants	<input type="radio"/>				
Other aspects of the application process (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please specify other aspects of the application process:

Q22

Did you contact SSHRC program staff for clarification on this program?

- Yes
- No

If yes, for which aspects of the application process did you need clarification or assistance?

Q23

Did you receive enough support from your institution during the application and selection process?

- Yes
- No

In what ways might institutions improve their support of applicants during this process?

Q24

What was your primary resource for program information?

- SSHRC program website
- SSHRC program staff
- Material provided by academic department
- Material provided by research office or grant office
- Academic department staf
- Research offices or grant office staf
- Other resource (*please specify below*)

Please specify other resource:

Q25

How can information on this program be better communicated to encourage appropriate applications or discourage inappropriate applications?

SSHRC GRANT AND OTHER FUNDING

Q26 Do you feel that the amount of money granted by SSHRC to your project was sufficient for your needs?

- More than sufficient
- Sufficient
- Less than sufficient
- Not sufficient

Please explain:

Q27 Do you feel you were given enough flexibility in terms of how the money was budgeted and could be spent?

- Yes
- No

If no, please specify:

Q28 Is three years a suitable period for completing your project?

- Yes
- No

If no, please specify:

Q29 What are the approximate proportions (%) of the total budget of your project that were covered by the SSHRC grant and by other sources of funding?

SSHRC grant (%)

Other sources of funding (%)

Q30 What was the source of this other financial support, and what was it primarily used for (e.g., equipment, facilities, travel, other resources, etc.)?

Q31

What proportion of your SSHRC grant did you use for:

Remuneration of students (%)

Travel (%)

Equipment/material (%)

Dissemination related activities (%)

Other (*please specify below*)

Please specify other:

Q32

Did the SSHRC project bring you new funding opportunities?

Yes

No

If yes, what kind of new opportunities?

Q33

What alternatives to the SSHRC Research/Creation grants exist in Canada for funding your research activities?

Q34

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **ADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q35

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **DISADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q36

Do you believe that you will resubmit an application for the program's next round of competition?

Yes

No

If not, please indicate your reason(s) for not resubmitting an application for the program's next round of competition:

Q37

Please share any additional comments you may have on the program, as well as any suggestions for its improvement:

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey!

Your responses, comments, and suggestions will be instrumental to the continuing development of SSHRC's Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program.

Please click on the "Submit" button.

Annex E – Survey Questionnaire: Unfunded Applicants

Survey Questionnaire Evaluation of SSHRC Research/Creation in the Fine Arts Pilot Program

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information from artist-researchers affiliated with Canadian postsecondary institutions who have applied to the SSHRC Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program for research grants.

Specifically, the main goal of the survey is to collect primary data on applicants' experiences with this program as well as information on the environment and conditions in which artist-researchers and students produce and evolve.

Ultimately, this survey will provide SSHRC management with data on the activities, outputs, and initial outcomes of this pilot program according to the following evaluation issues: i) program design and management, ii) program outputs and immediate outcomes, iii) program risks and opportunities, and iv) continued relevance and priorities.

This exercise constitutes the first external evaluation of the program. As such, your involvement is vital to the process.

The survey is being administered to all artist-researchers who have applied for funding in the first two competitions of this pilot program.

Please note that the individual answers provided in this survey will not be published. Rather, they will be compiled and aggregated in the analysis report.

The survey consists of 21 questions.

IMPORTANT: Please click on the "Submit" button at the end of the survey.

We thank you in advance for your cooperation.

Have a good survey!

GENERAL INFORMATION

Q1

In which artistic discipline(s) are you active?

- Architecture
- Design (including interior design)
- Creative writing
- Visual arts (painting, drawing, sculpture, ceramics, textiles)
- Dance
- Music
- Theatre, drama
- Film and video
- Media and electronic arts
- Performance arts
- Art education
- Interdisciplinary arts
- Other (*please specify below*)

Please specify (Other category):

Q2

What is the type/size of your post-secondary institution?

- Large-size university** (A large university has sponsored research expenditures of over \$30 million, a general operating percentage of over 20%, and greater than 30 doctoral programs)
- Medium-size university** (A medium university has sponsored research expenditures between \$10 million and \$30 million, a general operating percentage between 10% and 20%, and between 10 and 30 doctoral programs)
- Small-size university** (A small university has sponsored research expenditures of less than \$10 million, a general operating percentage of less than 10%, and less than 10 doctoral programs)
- University College
- Community College
- Cegep
- Other (please specify below)

Please specify (Other category):

Q3

In which Canadian region is your institution located?

- Atlantic (Newfoundland/Labrador, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia, New Brunswick)
- Quebec
- Ontario
- Prairies (Manitoba, Saskatchewan, Alberta)
- British Columbia
- Yukon, Nunavut and Northwest Territories

PROGRAM DEFINITION AND OBJECTIVES

Research/Creation has been defined by SSHRC as:

Research/creation (specific to the Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program): Any research activity or approach to research that forms an essential part of a creative process or artistic discipline and that directly fosters the creation of literary/artistic works. The research must address clear research questions, offer theoretical contextualization within the relevant field or fields of literary/artistic inquiry, and present a well considered methodological approach. Both the research and the resulting literary/artistic works must meet peer standards of excellence and be suitable for publication, public performance or viewing.

Q4 Do you find this definition appropriate as a basis for the program?

- Very appropriate
- Appropriate
- Somewhat appropriate
- Not appropriate

Q5 Could you suggest ways in which the definition could be improved?

Q6

Please rank the following program objectives according to their degree of relevance to your activities:

	<i>Very relevant</i>	<i>Relevant</i>	<i>Not very relevant</i>	<i>Not relevant</i>
Support high-quality research/creation in projects that advance knowledge in the fine arts and enhance the overall quality of artistic production in Canadian postsecondary institutions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop the research skills of graduate and undergraduate students who are working in artistic and related disciplines through their participation in programs of research that involve artistic practice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitate the dissemination and presentation of high quality work to a broad public through a diversity of scholarly and artistic means.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Foster opportunities for collaboration among university- and college-based artist-researchers, other university and college researchers, and professional artists.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q7

Should these objectives be modified to better support your research activities and the needs of artist-researchers?

Yes

No

If yes, please specify:

Q8

Please indicate the degree to which you were required to adapt/modify your research/creation project in your grant application to meet the criteria, requirements and objectives of the program:

	<i>Entirely</i>	<i>Significantl y</i>	<i>Moderately</i>	<i>Slightly</i>	<i>Not at all</i>
Artistic discipline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Area of research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research/creation questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creation program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Methodology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expected impact/results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dissemination and presentation of results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Team composition and role of collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Training of students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CV and other credentials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If other, please specify:

PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

Please note that when answering the questions in this section, you are to refer to the most recent application you submitted (for either the 2003 or 2005 competition) to the SSHRC Research/Creation program.

Q9 Please rank the following aspects of the application process according to their degree of adequacy:

	<i>Very adequate</i>	<i>Adequate</i>	<i>Somewhat adequate</i>	<i>Not adequate</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Clarity of instruction for the application process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transparency, fairness, and appropriateness of evaluation criteria	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Description of various categories of eligible applicants/participants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Comprehensiveness of listed areas of art research/disciplines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Availability of application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amount of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Relevance of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ease of use of SSHRC's online CV form and related instruction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amount of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Relevance of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time given to complete the application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Timing of application announcements/deadlines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Adjudication and peer review process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantity of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall SSHRC client support provided to applicants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other aspects of the application process (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please specify other aspects of the application process:

Q10

Did you contact SSHRC program staff for clarification on this program?

- Yes
- No

If yes, for which aspects of the application process did you need clarification or assistance?

Q11

Did you receive enough support from your institution during the application and selection process?

- Yes
- No

In what ways might institutions improve their support of applicants during this process?

Q12

What was your primary resource for program information?

- SSHRC program website
- SSHRC program staff
- Material provided by academic department
- Material provided by research office or grant office
- Academic department staf
- Research offices or grant office staf
- Other resource (*please specify below*)

Please specify other resource:

Q13

How can information on this program be better communicated to encourage appropriate applications or discourage inappropriate applications?

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for the user to provide their answer to the question. The box is currently blank.

SSHRC GRANT AND OTHER FUNDING

Please note that when answering the questions in this section, you are to refer to the most recent research/creation project you submitted (for either the 2003 or 2005 competition) to the SSHRC Research/Creation program.

Q14 To what extent did your project proceed despite not being supported by SSHRC?

- The project proceeded in its entirety
- Most of the parts of the project proceeded
- Only a few parts of the project proceeded
- The project did not proceed at all

Please specify the parts of the projects that did not proceed:

Q15 Did you find other sources of funding for your planned research/creation activities?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was the source of this other financial support, and what was it primarily used for (e.g., equipment, facilities, travel, other resources, etc.)?

Q16 In what ways did not being funded impact your activities and practices? Conversely, what might have been the impact of receiving the grant?

Q17

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **ADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q18

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **DISADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q19

Do you believe that you will resubmit an application for the program's next round of competition?

- Yes
- No

If not, please indicate your reason(s) for not resubmitting an application for the program's next round of competition:

Q20 What might be some of the long-term impacts of this program for Canadian art and creation research capabilities (and beyond)? Conversely, what might be some of the effects of not pursuing this pilot program?

Q21 Please share any additional comments you may have on the program, as well as any suggestions for its improvement:

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey!

Your responses, comments, and suggestions will be instrumental to the continuing development of SSHRC's Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program.

Please click on the "Submit" button.

Annex F – Survey Questionnaire: Managers and Grant Officers

Survey Questionnaire Evaluation of SSHRC Research/Creation in the Fine Arts Pilot Program

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information from artist-researchers affiliated with Canadian postsecondary institutions who have applied to the SSHRC Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program for research grants.

Specifically, the main goal of the survey is to collect primary data on applicants' experiences with this program as well as information on the environment and conditions in which artist-researchers and students produce and evolve.

Ultimately, this survey will provide SSHRC management with data on the activities, outputs, and initial outcomes of this pilot program according to the following evaluation issues: i) program design and management, ii) program outputs and immediate outcomes, iii) program risks and opportunities, and iv) continued relevance and priorities.

This exercise constitutes the first external evaluation of the program. As such, your involvement is vital to the process.

The survey is being administered to all artist-researchers who have applied for funding in the first two competitions of this pilot program.

Please note that the individual answers provided in this survey will not be published. Rather, they will be compiled and aggregated in the analysis report.

The survey consists of 21 questions.

IMPORTANT: Please click on the "Submit" button at the end of the survey.

We thank you in advance for your cooperation.

Have a good survey!

GENERAL INFORMATION

Q1

In which artistic discipline(s) are you active?

- Architecture
- Design (including interior design)
- Creative writing
- Visual arts (painting, drawing, sculpture, ceramics, textiles)
- Dance
- Music
- Theatre, drama
- Film and video
- Media and electronic arts
- Performance arts
- Art education
- Interdisciplinary arts
- Other (*please specify below*)

Please specify (Other category):

Q2

What is the type/size of your post-secondary institution?

- Large-size university** (A large university has sponsored research expenditures of over \$30 million, a general operating percentage of over 20%, and greater than 30 doctoral programs)
- Medium-size university** (A medium university has sponsored research expenditures between \$10 million and \$30 million, a general operating percentage between 10% and 20%, and between 10 and 30 doctoral programs)
- Small-size university** (A small university has sponsored research expenditures of less than \$10 million, a general operating percentage of less than 10%, and less than 10 doctoral programs)
- University College
- Community College
- Cegep
- Other (please specify below)

Please specify (Other category):

Q3

In which Canadian region is your institution located?

- Atlantic (Newfoundland/Labrador, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia, New Brunswick)
- Quebec
- Ontario
- Prairies (Manitoba, Saskatchewan, Alberta)
- British Columbia
- Yukon, Nunavut and Northwest Territories

PROGRAM DEFINITION AND OBJECTIVES

Research/Creation has been defined by SSHRC as:

Research/creation (specific to the Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program): Any research activity or approach to research that forms an essential part of a creative process or artistic discipline and that directly fosters the creation of literary/artistic works. The research must address clear research questions, offer theoretical contextualization within the relevant field or fields of literary/artistic inquiry, and present a well considered methodological approach. Both the research and the resulting literary/artistic works must meet peer standards of excellence and be suitable for publication, public performance or viewing.

Q4 Do you find this definition appropriate as a basis for the program?

- Very appropriate
- Appropriate
- Somewhat appropriate
- Not appropriate

Q5 Could you suggest ways in which the definition could be improved?

Q6

Please rank the following program objectives according to their degree of relevance to your activities:

	<i>Very relevant</i>	<i>Relevant</i>	<i>Not very relevant</i>	<i>Not relevant</i>
Support high-quality research/creation in projects that advance knowledge in the fine arts and enhance the overall quality of artistic production in Canadian postsecondary institutions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop the research skills of graduate and undergraduate students who are working in artistic and related disciplines through their participation in programs of research that involve artistic practice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitate the dissemination and presentation of high quality work to a broad public through a diversity of scholarly and artistic means.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Foster opportunities for collaboration among university- and college-based artist-researchers, other university and college researchers, and professional artists.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q7

Should these objectives be modified to better support your research activities and the needs of artist-researchers?

Yes

No

If yes, please specify:

Q8

Please indicate the degree to which you were required to adapt/modify your research/creation project in your grant application to meet the criteria, requirements and objectives of the program:

	<i>Entirely</i>	<i>Significantl y</i>	<i>Moderately</i>	<i>Slightly</i>	<i>Not at all</i>
Artistic discipline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Area of research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research/creation questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creation program/orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Methodology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expected impact/results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dissemination and presentation of results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Team composition and role of collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Training of students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CV and other credentials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If other, please specify:

PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

Please note that when answering the questions in this section, you are to refer to the most recent application you submitted (for either the 2003 or 2005 competition) to the SSHRC Research/Creation program.

Q9 Please rank the following aspects of the application process according to their degree of adequacy:

	<i>Very adequate</i>	<i>Adequate</i>	<i>Somewhat adequate</i>	<i>Not adequate</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Clarity of instruction for the application process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transparency, fairness, and appropriateness of evaluation criteria	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Description of various categories of eligible applicants/participants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Comprehensiveness of listed areas of art research/disciplines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Availability of application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amount of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Relevance of information requested in the application form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ease of use of SSHRC's online CV form and related instruction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amount of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Relevance of information requested in the online CV form	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time given to complete the application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Timing of application announcements/deadlines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Adjudication and peer review process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantity of feedback received on application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall SSHRC client support provided to applicants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other aspects of the application process (<i>please specify below</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please specify other aspects of the application process:

Q10

Did you contact SSHRC program staff for clarification on this program?

- Yes
- No

If yes, for which aspects of the application process did you need clarification or assistance?

Q11

Did you receive enough support from your institution during the application and selection process?

- Yes
- No

In what ways might institutions improve their support of applicants during this process?

Q12

What was your primary resource for program information?

- SSHRC program website
- SSHRC program staff
- Material provided by academic department
- Material provided by research office or grant office
- Academic department staf
- Research offices or grant office staf
- Other resource (*please specify below*)

Please specify other resource:

Q13

How can information on this program be better communicated to encourage appropriate applications or discourage inappropriate applications?

SSHRC GRANT AND OTHER FUNDING

Please note that when answering the questions in this section, you are to refer to the most recent research/creation project you submitted (for either the 2003 or 2005 competition) to the SSHRC Research/Creation program.

Q14 To what extent did your project proceed despite not being supported by SSHRC?

- The project proceeded in its entirety
- Most of the parts of the project proceeded
- Only a few parts of the project proceeded
- The project did not proceed at all

Please specify the parts of the projects that did not proceed:

Q15 Did you find other sources of funding for your planned research/creation activities?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was the source of this other financial support, and what was it primarily used for (e.g., equipment, facilities, travel, other resources, etc.)?

Q16 In what ways did not being funded impact your activities and practices? Conversely, what might have been the impact of receiving the grant?

Q17

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **ADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q18

Based on your experience and knowledge of this program, please indicate its main **DISADVANTAGES** in terms of its structure, management and execution:

Q19

Do you believe that you will resubmit an application for the program's next round of competition?

- Yes
- No

If not, please indicate your reason(s) for not resubmitting an application for the program's next round of competition:

Q20 What might be some of the long-term impacts of this program for Canadian art and creation research capabilities (and beyond)? Conversely, what might be some of the effects of not pursuing this pilot program?

Q21 Please share any additional comments you may have on the program, as well as any suggestions for its improvement:

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey!

Your responses, comments, and suggestions will be instrumental to the continuing development of SSHRC's Research/Creation Grants in Fine Arts program.

Please click on the "Submit" button.